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Defining Green Occupational Groups in the Spanish Vocational Education and Training System: An Emerging Approach

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Abstract

Purpose: The aim of this paper is to propose a categorisation of green VET occupational groups within Spain's VET system that matches the growing workplace, socio-political and environmental demands. We hypothesize that the green component of Spanish VET is mainly present in core activities related to sectors linked to energy, the environment and environmental sustainability and shows room for improvement in comparison with other qualifications.

Methods: This paper conducts an in-depth literature review to analyse the treatment of green VET occupational groups at both the theoretical and empirical level. Quantitative research is also conducted by means of secondary source data analysis.

Findings: The research is still under way, but the initial results appear to confirm the main hypothesis: Spain's green VET can be framed and positioned within the VET supply system as a new grouping requiring formal identification and definition in order to be promoted and given broader scope.

Conclusions: This paper provides an initial outline of the scope of the green VET offering via those qualifications directly related to renewable energy and the environment. In the future, this initial approach will need to be extended to the other occupational groups in order to gain an understanding of the extent to which Spain's VET systems are ready for the green transition.

Keywords

vocational education and training in Spain, environmental sustainability, green occupational groups

1 Introduction

1.1 The context

In the vocational education and training (VET) context, the environment has usually been viewed from an anthropocentric epistemological perspective as an economic resource or social determinant. From this standpoint, going green is a cost factor, not a purpose in itself. The conceptualisation of VET is rooted in the capitalist industrial revolution, systematisation and integration of which into education and training systems — as reflected in the productivist theories of human capital (Giddens, 1994; Rees, 1990) — took place in the 20th century. In this first iteration, VET's role was limited to providing skilled workers for a constantly growing and expanding industrial fabric in which the environment was perceived as a source of limitless resources. After the Second World War, and with the advance of the welfare state, education and vocational training systems started to also be considered drivers of well-being, inclusion and social equity, a shift reflected in the critical theories that emerged (realism, structuralism, feminism, etc.) (Suart, 2018) and in the concept of sustainable human development (with the focus on skills, equitable access, pathways into work, etc.) (Elder, 2015; Bonvin, 2018, McGrath et al., 2022). The environment, however, continued to be viewed as a background issue, albeit now from the perspective of limited resources and climate risk.

The second stage of environmental awareness in VET stems from the international agenda which, with the Brundtland Report, clearly set out the finite and limited nature of our planet when viewed from the perspective of human development (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). Under this framework, a new vision of the economy emerged that entailed a shift towards environmental protection and regulation and development of the green economy. In line with this, UNESCO began a move towards Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and green VET (UNEVOC, 2017), in which greater emphasis is nevertheless placed on social aspects, equity and education quality than on the environment (Finlayson et al., 2021). Although the environment acquires new prominence, it is primarily formulated in terms of environmental protection and climate change mitigation combined with a focus on efficient use of resources and confidence in the ability of technology to address environmental challenges; a change of production and consumption model is not prioritised (Pavlova, 2009). This implied maintaining VET's role as a provider of skilled workers, though now in a context of resource scarcity, alongside a focus on sustainable human development, principally in terms of employability. In this regard, the German government was a pioneer in linking the green economy to the VET system (Fien & Wilson, 2005; UNPD, 2015) through creation of new employment opportunities: *'in the context of an ecologically oriented transformation of the economy, occupational profiles and curricula need to be expanded and renewed with respect to the protection of the environment and resources as well as renewable energies'* (Mertineit, 2013, 16). The German case exemplifies the conceptual shift from provision of skilled workers to provision and assurance of the competences required by green industry (energy and environment) with the aim of fostering sustainable competitiveness (at regional, national and other levels) founded on the green economy. From the theoretical perspective of the political economy of skills, VET becomes a provider of competences to broader competence ecosystems as well as to the green economy. The logic behind this is that, by providing skilled workers and competences, the VET system contributes to reducing the mismatch between skills training and business demand, thereby fostering sustainable competitiveness (Lucas et al., 2018).

The third stage of awareness is related to environmental sustainability, which advocates decoupling VET from the economy (either traditional or green) and adopting a new ecology-centred ethos, thereby breaking with the anthropocentric epistemological tradition, an approach proposed, albeit timidly, in the literature (Anderson, 2009). Under this perspective, education

and learning would focus on the planet and the ecology, not on the productive sector or learners. Although there have been a few attempts to incorporate ecologism into education, the progress made in this regard has been limited (Pavlova, 2009).

It can therefore be affirmed that there is no well-established theoretical body of work on environmental sustainability in the field of vocational education and training (Goldney et al., 2007; McGrath & Powell, 2016).

1.2 Purpose of the research

This paper will analyse VET in Spain from the perspective of the green economy, examining the training available to both young people and adults in terms of green occupational profiles. The challenges of a circular and low-carbon economy are reflected in professional profiles and occupations in all sectors, given that all economic activities require resources and energy (Amanatidis & Laky, 2019). The European scenario of a decarbonised economy by 2050 entails changes in current occupational profiles (Cedefop, 2022), which requires a look at the structure of the current VET system itself.

The aim of this paper is to propose a categorisation of green VET occupational groups within Spain's VET system that matches the growing workplace, socio-political and environmental demands, addressing them from the perspective of the green economy. Unlike other classifications of occupational groups, either related to sectoral areas (e.g. industrial occupational groups) (Gamboa et al., 2021), technological ones (e.g. STEM) (STEAM Euskadi, 2018) or ICT (based on Calvino et al., 2018), there is currently a lack of conceptualisation and classification of green occupational groups in Spain's VET system.

The main hypothesis of this study, from the supply perspective, is the existence of green vocational occupational groups within the current VET offering in Spain deserving formal categorisation so as to enable their development and improvement in light of the aforementioned challenges. From a demand perspective, we hypothesize that the green component of Spanish VET is mainly present in core activities related to sectors linked to renewable energy, the environment and environmental sustainability and shows room for improvement in comparison with other qualifications.

Based on this approach, an analytical framework for understanding green occupational groups is presented in terms of the main sectors providing green services. Although green occupations and employment occupy cross-cutting positions in all value chains, the scope of this study is limited to economic activities and sectors that directly provide services involving natural and renewable energy resources and are considered drivers of the European economy's green transition as set out in the European Green Deal (Cedefop & OECD, 2022). Traditionally, in the Spanish context, economic activities associated with the environment were classified according to the sectors that provided services involved in the management of key environmental resources, and whose sectoral growth was closely associated with the environmental regulations set at European level. These classifications were heterogeneous and related to the management of the planet's main resources, e.g. waste management, resource efficiency (efficient manufacturing and eco-design), soil decontamination, the integrated water cycle, and air and ecosystems. However, since climate change became a key driver of the European agenda, the energy sector occupies a significant position as an active component of climate change, as stated in the European Green Deal (Amanatidis & Laky, 2019).

This study is therefore based on a proprietary working definition of the green occupational groups that spans a significant number of qualifications required by the activities that the ILO (2013) considers to forming part of the provision of environmental goods and services.

The relevance of this paper is twofold. On the one hand, it is part of the transition towards a green economy in which the VET system offers an almost untried lever for decarbonising the European and Spanish economy by 2050 (European Commission, Joint Research Centre, 2022)

based on more sustainable resource use, reducing dependency on energy imports and creating a circular economy. In this sense, understanding the structure of green occupational groups in Spain's VET system is key, as the EU's and Spain's success in becoming a climate-neutral economy by 2050 will be strongly tied to developing the skills of human capital. On the other hand, it is a topic barely studied in VET research.

2 Methods

The methodology used to define the green occupational groups within the Spanish VET system was developed in various stages.

First, the sectors of activity in which there is demand for green vocational qualifications were identified. To this end, a literature review was conducted, identifying two distinct classes of business activity that could be considered green (ILO, 2013): the classification of environmental protection activities (CEPA) and the classification of resource management activities (CReMA). These classifications contain the distinct activities described by Fernández Gómez and Larrea Basterra (2022) — 75 activities grouped into 9 categories in the case of the CEPA and 10 activities in the case of the CReMA.

Next, the vocational areas and qualifications currently taught in both Initial VET and Continuous VET, irrespective of occupational group and as listed by the Instituto Vasco de Conocimiento de la Formación Profesional (IVAC, 2022), were identified. From the overall group of vocational areas and qualifications, those that bore either a direct or indirect relationship to the CEPA and CReMA, and the occupational groups of which they form part, were selected. Direct relationships were identified via the name of the activity and the description of the content of the vocational qualifications listed by the Instituto Nacional de las Cualificaciones (INCUAL, 2023). Indirect relationships were identified in qualifications that referred to development of the skills necessary to perform activities requiring knowledge of environmental regulation or of techniques designed to protect the environment or minimise the risks to it.

Therefore, the basic unit of analysis used to identify the green occupational groups is the vocational qualification and its relationship to the activities involving environmental goods and services. These qualifications are defined as “*a set of standards of competence relevant to employment that can be acquired through modular or other types of training and work experience (Royal Decree 1128/2003 of 5 September 2003 regulating the national catalogue of vocational qualifications)*” (INCUAL, 2023).

3 Findings

The analysis performed has yielded a set of occupational groups that could be identified as green as they directly provide qualifications relevant to the performance of a high percentage of activities listed in the CEPA and CReMA. It can therefore be affirmed that they are a strong source of environmental qualifications. This set is made up of the Safety and Environment (SaE) group, which covers 66.7% of the CEPA via eight qualifications, and the Energy and Water (EaW) group, which covers 11% of the CEPA (via two qualifications) and 40% of the CReMA (via 13 qualifications).

A second set of occupational groups that constitute a medium-strength source of qualifications related to green goods and services has also been identified. This set comprises the Farming (covering 20% of the CReMA) and Equipment Installation and Maintenance (11% of the CEPA, 10% of the CReMA) occupational groups (Table 1). The occupational groups categorised as being a weak source of environmental qualifications have been excluded from this analysis because of their negligible impact.

Table 1

Occupational groups with strong or medium-strength links with the environmental goods and services sector, by number of qualifications available and CEPA and CReMA activities affected

Strength of link	Occupational group	No of qualifications by type of CEPA or CReMA activity	% of CEPA or CReMA activities affected by the qualifications (as % of total CEPA or CReMA activities)
Strong	Safety and Environment (SaE)	8 CEPA	66.7% of CEPA
Strong	Energy and Water (EaW)	2 CEPA 13 CReMA	11.1% of CEPA 40% of CReMA
Medium	Farming (FARM)	2 CReMA	20% of CReMA
Medium	Equipment Installation and Maintenance (EIaM)	1 CEPA 2 CReMA	11.1% of CEPA 10% of CReMA

Source: Compiled in-house from Fernández Gómez and Larrea Basterra (2022), IVAC (2022) and INCUAL (2023)

Tables 2 and 3 show a breakdown of the specific activities listed in the CEPA and CReMA and the VET qualifications, areas and occupational groups related to them.

Table 2

CEPA activities (1 digit) linked to the environmental goods and services sector and closely related qualifications and occupational groups

Specific activity	Vocational qualification	Vocational area	Occupational group
1. Protection of ambient air and climate	Control of air pollution	Environmental Management	SaE
2. Wastewater management	Operation of water treatment plants	Environmental Management	SaE
	Installation and maintenance of water networks	Water	EaW
	Management and monitoring of installation and maintenance of water and sewerage networks and facilities	Water	EaW
	Installation and maintenance of building water supply and drainage facilities	Electromechanical maintenance	EIaM
3. Waste management	Collection, sorting and initial storage of waste	Environmental Management	SaE
	Waste management	Environmental Management	SaE
4. Protection and remediation of soil, groundwater and surface water	Cleaning in open spaces and industrial facilities	Environmental Management	SaE
5. Noise and vibration abatement	Noise and vibration control and sound insulation	Environmental Management	SaE
6. Protection of	-	-	-

biodiversity and landscapes			
7. Protection against radiation	-	-	-
8. Environmental research and development	-	-	-
9. Other environmental protection activities	Environmental education and awareness-raising	Environmental Management	SaE
	Environmental Management	Environmental Management	SaE

Source: Compiled in-house from Fernández Gómez and Larrea Basterra (2022), IVAC (2022) and INCUAL (2023)

Note: Safety and Environment (SaE), Energy and Water (EaW), Equipment Installation and Maintenance (EIaM).

Table 3

CReMA activities linked to the environmental goods and services sector and closely related qualifications and occupational groups

Specific activity	Vocational qualification	Vocational area	Occupational group
10. Management of water	Management of efficient water use	Energy efficiency	EaW
11.A Management of forest areas	Management of afforestation and forestry practices	Forestry	FARM
11.B Minimisation of the intake of forest resources	Auxiliary woodland conservation and improvement activities	Forestry	FARM
12. Management of wild flora and fauna	-	-	-
13.A Production of energy from renewable resources	Auxiliary renewable energy plant installation and maintenance operations	Renewable energy	EaW
	Installation and maintenance of solar thermal plants	Renewable energy	EaW
	Installation and maintenance of solar photovoltaic plants	Renewable energy	EaW
	Installation and maintenance of closed-circuit geexchange systems	Renewable energy	EaW
	Management of installation and maintenance of wind farms	Renewable energy	EaW
	Planning and development of solar photovoltaic plants	Renewable energy	EaW
	Planning and development of solar thermal plants	Renewable energy	EaW
	Management of closed-circuit geexchange plants	Renewable energy	EaW
13.B Heat/energy saving and management	Building energy efficiency	Energy efficiency	EaW
	Energy auditing	Energy efficiency	EaW

	Installation of heat and sound insulation systems and of fire and radon protection in buildings	Installation and assembly	BaCW
	Installation and maintenance of heat and sound insulation systems and fire protection	Insulation systems	EIaM
	Management and supervision of installation and maintenance of heat and sound insulation systems and fire protection	Insulation systems	EIaM
13.C Minimisation of the use of fossil energy as raw materials	Planning and development of solar photovoltaic plants	Renewable energy	EaW
	Planning and development of solar thermal plants	Renewable energy	EaW
14. Management of minerals	-	-	-
15. Research and development activities for resource management	-	-	-
16. Other resource management activities	-	-	-

Source: Compiled in-house from Fernández Gómez and Larrea Basterra (2022), IVAC (2022) and INCUAL (2023)

Note: Energy and Water (EaW), Farming (FARM), Building and Civil Works (BaCW), Installation and Maintenance (IaM). Codes 11 and 13 are not included in the table because it is understood that they are represented by 11.A, 11.B, 13.A, 13.B and 13.C.

4 Discussion

The research is still under way, but the initial results appear to confirm the main hypothesis: Spain's green VET can be framed and positioned within the VET supply system as a new grouping requiring formal identification and definition in order to be promoted and given broader scope.

The objective of this analysis was to propose a preliminary selection of green occupational groups found in Spain's VET system. To this end, the occupational groups associated with the qualifications required to perform activities in the environmental goods and services sector have been identified.

Although two occupational groups considered to be core to green employment (SaE and EaW) have been identified, the SaE group comprises two completely separate areas, one focused on the environment and the other on safety with no relation to the environment. Therefore, this occupational group's strong green emphasis is only found in one part of it (the environmental side). Conversely, while the EaW occupational group is largely devoted to environmental goods and services, it covers a smaller percentage of activities. Consequently, in addition to identifying the green occupational groups, the analysis needs to be broken down into specific training programmes and occupational certificates directly linked to this area.

Although it is clear that there should be a typology of specific core occupational groups developing the skills required by the environmental goods and services industry, there is

currently an intermediate layer of groups that offer fewer qualifications for the sectors covered by the CEPA and CReMA. The latter have the potential to be even greener and, in the future, could be rated as medium-strength and strong sources given their environmental importance (e.g. Building and Civil Works, and Farming).

In this regard, the analysis conducted indicates that the current range of qualifications does not cover all the activities in the CEPA and CReMA, which is striking given their relevance and, at the same time, opens a window of opportunity for VET. Therefore, an analysis of present and future demand for the activities could indicate the priorities for VET to address, their intensity and the gaps in supply. In this regard, the greater availability of information on workplace demand and the green economy than on the training available in this field is noteworthy.

Future research will require deeper analysis and the involvement of expert opinion on the occupational groups (supply) and activities involved (demand), as well as more detailed exploration of the other occupational groups, as there may be other less evident relationships not detected in this analysis.

5 Conclusion

This paper provides an initial outline of the scope of the green VET offering via those qualifications directly related to energy and the environment. In the future, this initial approach will need to be extended to the other occupational groups in order to gain an understanding of the extent to which Spain's VET systems are ready for the green transition.

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